

NETWORKS OF SOCIOLINGUISTICS

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Abstract: Before looking at the importance of sociolinguistics, we should pay attention to the terms "internal" and "external" in sociolinguistics. If a society uses its own language of the nation and the state, it is an internal language, and if a society uses second and third languages besides its mother tongue, it is a foreign language.

Key words: listener, person, linguistics, term, sociolinguistics, theory, social life.

As we have seen, sociolinguistic manifestations do not fundamentally change the language, but enrich it, make it easier to use, and optimize it. The development of inter-country relations prepares the ground for the rapprochement of the cultures of the peoples and peoples living in those countries, as a result, languages also influence each other, such cooperation, in turn, ensures the internal development of languages. American linguist R. Bell said that there are two directions in the field of sociolinguistics.

a) pure sociolinguistics, in which the grammar of the speaker and the listener, their influence on each other, and their cooperation are studied.

b) sociology of language, in which the issues of the use of language signs and symbols in various social aspects of society are studied.

In this regard, American linguists call the first direction microsociology, and the second direction macrosociology. Sociologists deal with this problem. Microsociolinguistics studies the speech cooperative relations of individuals forming small social groups. Macrosociolinguistics studies speech communication between one social group and another. We can find many opinions of linguists about macrosociolinguistics. One of them says: "Macro-sociolinguistics focuses on the sociolinguistic characteristics of language use within large social groups within a country (gender, age, education). Linguists have mainly conducted more scientific research on language specificity, language-related communication, and problematic situations in this direction. Therefore, in macrosociolinguistics, the communication process of large groups on the scale of the existing society occupies the main place, and language and speech features in the interaction of people in that society are studied. In addition, we can say that social groups occupy the main place in

sociolinguistics. Because the users of the language belong to a certain group of the social stratum. In any modern human society, there are different groups according to gender, age, place, education, social class characteristics, at the same time, each group has different characteristics according to the conditions and goals, and accordingly, their language usage characteristics are also different. According to this situation, forms of social language were formed. Therefore, the language also changes as social life changes and differs somewhat from its historical appearance. We mentioned that people unite for a common goal, but social groups are a more difficult concept to understand, because they are not only formally and informally united, but also consist of people with close social views. Social groups do not form mutual groups with each other, they belong to the same group from a social point of view. They are naturally united. Also, micro-sociolinguistics sociolinguistically analyzes language-related relations between small groups (family, colleagues, neighbors). Microsociolinguistics mainly deals with non-individual large-scale speech patterns and informal language patterns of small groups.

On the basis of microsociolinguistics, a person and his way of using language, as well as the communication style of people gathered in social groups such as family, school, work, are studied in this group, and the forms of communication are reformed. In this regard, one of the linguists V. Kulisnihenko thinks: "Social groups can be large and small according to their scale. For example, groups based on ethnicity, religion, age and gender, and social class are considered large and broad, while subgroups based on kinship or occupation are considered small. Instead, they can be included in large groups, any person can belong to one or more social groups, social groups can be divided into primary and secondary groups. Primary groups are considered to be directly related and permanent groups.

The term primary and secondary social groups was brought to science by C. Cooley, according to him, primary groups are built directly on personal relationships, have a deeper root and are groups based on stable relations. For example, groups based on characteristics such as nationality, family, gender are primary because we are permanent members of this group. Secondary groups are religion, age, occupation. That is, speech associations can be professional colleagues who share some common jargon, hip-hop fans or high school students, as well as family friends. Members of speech associations use various slangs and jargons to promote the group's goals and objectives. Also, according to A. Kepel, the term "sociolinguistics" defines itself. As its name suggests, sociolinguistics is a science that arose at the intersection of sociology and linguistics. The interdisciplinary nature of sociolinguistics is

recognized by most researchers. The term sociolinguistics was introduced to science for the first time in 1952 by the American sociologist G. Curry.

Problems related to sociolinguistics were raised in the articles of linguists, sociologists, cultural anthropologists, dialectologists and various experts in the field of communication of the 1950s, included in J. Fishman's collection "Lectures in Language in Society". According to some sociolinguists, the roots of sociolinguistics should be sought not in American linguistics, but in European, in particular, Russian linguistics. In the formation of sociolinguistics, I.A. Baudouin de Courtenay's research on the social conditioning of language phenomena, as well as the impact of extralinguistic social factors on the use and development of language, played a major role. I.A. Baudouin de Courtenay said that "language exists only in the society of people, so we should always pay attention to its social side as well as its spiritual side. Not only individual psychology, but also sociology should serve as the basis of linguistics. In the first half of the 20th century, French, Russian, and Czech linguistic schools paid great attention to the social nature of languages. Russian linguists I.A. Beaudoin de Courtenay, Y. Polivanov, L. Yakubinsky, B. Larin. The scientific ideas of linguists such as Sh.Bally motivated the formation of sociolinguistics as a science. American researcher U. Labov, one of the founders of modern sociolinguistics, defined sociolinguistics as a science that studies "language in its social context". That is, sociolinguists do not pay attention to the language, nor to the study of its internal structure. They mainly study how people in a particular society use language. All the social factors affecting it are taken into account, from the age, gender, culture and level of education of the participants to the specific speech act. According to U. Bright, sociolinguistic research is related to the relationship between language and society. However, such a view also creates uncertainty. If we clarify this, then language and society are not just a set of units, but they are structures. In this case, the sociolinguist's task is to reveal the system of mutual relations in the language structure and social structure. That is, the task of sociolinguists is to show the systematic joint variation of the linguistic structure, and even to reveal the accidental connection of one or another direction.

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